

THE STUDY OF TEACHING ENGLISH ONLINE

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Annotation. Distance learning is progressively being brought into the instructive interaction. Hence, the quest for advancements in the improvement of techniques and advancements for such classes is viewed as really important. Specifically, researchers work in such regions: expanding the power of classes; extension of content; building individual directions for every understudy, considering his capacities and the persuasive and esteem circle of character; strengthening of learners' free work. Despite the fact that distance learning has showed up generally as of late, it has proactively turned into a serious instructive component, has shown off itself abilities as a promising educational innovation. This sort of class is acquiring fame because of the individual methodology, considering the understudy's confidence, persuading him and involving the most recent mechanical devices in the preparation cycle.

Keywords: teaching English; online teaching; Internet; foreign language; benefits of teaching English remotely; distance learning.

Introduction. If a couple of years prior, distance learning included sending preparing materials through mail, presently, because of the improvement of innovation, this interaction happens through the Internet, through email or through Skype. This approach has numerous positive viewpoints, the principal of which is the capacity of the understudy to connect with at a helpful time for him any place where there is admittance to the organization. Normally, the educator's plan for getting work done ought to likewise be considered, yet you can constantly concur with him and some way or another change your arrangements.

Regardless, doing at home for some hot tea, you can recollect and learn all that far superior to in the study halls of the instructional hub. The exploration interaction utilized the techniques for objectivity, rationale, investigation and blend of logical information. Throughout this exploration, the significance of Bloom's scientific categorization was impartially uncovered. Potential troubles in distance learning English. Above all else, we are discussing absolutely

specialized explanations behind the disturbance of the instructive cycle, - PC breakdown, camera, breaks in Internet correspondences and so forth.

Furthermore, participation, essentially insignificant, between learners gives a really substantial outcome. 4) Foreign distance learning courses give extraordinary consideration to the correspondence of learners with one another in topical discussions and on informal organizations, which decidedly affects the consequence of preparing. Such strategies ought to likewise be utilized in English courses. What are the issues of full-time English guidance in instructive establishments? The ongoing act of full-time educating of English in Uzbekistan experiences various issues. This is one more justification behind those wishing to get familiar with an unknown dialect utilizing far off strategies.

What are these issues and are distance courses totally absent any and all these weaknesses? 1) Current procedures are not ideal. The time and exertion that is spent on every understudy is very perfect, however even on account of high instructor capability and division of the gathering into a few subgroups, the consequences of preparing can't be called ideal. 2) Insufficient force of casual planning of learners. 3) Poor fundamental planning and too quick progress from regenerative work to useful work. 4) The adverse consequence of different sorts of long breaks in preparing, prompting the forgetting of material recently scholarly. 5) Lack of proposals that are adequately useful to address and forestall lacks in the securing of information and conversational abilities among learners. 6) A ton of holes in crafted by the understudy information evaluation framework. 7) Unsatisfactory choice of visual guides and low instructive impact of their application. Remote learning of English, by utilizing the Internet, as a strategy for understanding the data privileges of all members in this cycle.

The data freedoms and commitments of learners are by and large not in struggle with one another. Indeed, even in actuality, they complete one another in execution. Learning English and self-instruction are a solitary constant course of data immersion. The benefit of the data directly over the commitment suggests opportunity of admittance to any instructive materials, not controlled not entirely set in stone by the prerequisites of the schooling system. On the off chance that the data obligation wins in the growing experience, the individual data climate of the understudy is fundamentally limited and stops at such a degree of improvement that meets the base obligatory necessities. Further restricting of the climate can prompt systemic and mechanical exhaustion of the instructive cycle, because of the severance of associations among items and conclusion in an extremely restricted data space. Subsequently, a huge

diminishing in the viability of classes can be noticed. Accordingly, admittance to data can't be restricted to any structure, every one of the instructive entertainers ought to have the option to utilize the whole volume of data at any helpful time. Be that as it may, the accommodation of information ought to be completed in stages, as per instructive guidelines, composed by the school system and overseen by English educators. The educator is obliged to initiate the capability of the understudy, his insight base and character, make him a free unit of the showing framework and direct him to the new pinnacles of information. The latest thing in showing unknown dialects is to change to a by and by situated school system, which, as a subsystem, ought to contain an understudy.

Conclusion. Distance learning of English through Skype. Regarding the further improvement of electronic advances, distance learning has gotten new open doors. All things considered, by directing unknown dialect preparing in Skype, you can offer understudies the chance to dominate it in a brief time frame. Some of the time the distance between the instructor and the understudy can arrive at a few a large number of kilometers, however it doesn't make any difference. The educator can change the way to express words, the development of designs in sentences, as well as give some other suggestions on the showing approach than if he were in a similar room as the understudy and the expense, while staying open to by far most of occupants of the Russian Federation. In this way, it merits exploiting every one of the benefits that can be acquired by gaining English utilizing Skype from an educator with an adequately high capability.

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